

Welcome to the 8th volume of the EU-HIP Newsletter!

Dear Reader, we wish you a great start of the New Year- May 2026 be a successful year accompanied by health. We kick-off this year with a special issue of our Newsletter which presents to you some of the highlights from the Country visit report of Iceland. In addition to that, we will introduce you to the JA STOCKPILE project and provide news from HERA.

Let's dive into this volume!

Getting deeper insight: meet Iceland!

Followed by the Landscape analysis performed earlier by the EU-HIP Consortium, our partners perform semi-structured interviews with experts in several countries in order to gain better insight into the functionality of IT systems, roles and interactions of key stakeholders and details about national legislation. In this volume we will focus on the results of this analysis performed in Iceland.

During a three-day visit we have performed interviews with representatives of several institutions which play a key role in Iceland's governance of health-related data, cross-sectoral cooperation, decision making and maintenance of the country's health threat preparedness. A conclusion can be drawn that Iceland has a strong digital backbone enabling a data-driven approach in combating future crises.

At the heart of its infrastructure is Hekla - an electronic communication network for sending health data between entities and gathering information into centralized databases, operated by the National Centre for e-Health. All Icelandic health-related authorities, institutions and pharmacies are connected to the system and data is continuously collected from each healthcare centre infrastructure.

The National Centre for e-Health operates Saga - the primary patient electronic health record (EHR) system which documents patient information, health conditions and interactions with healthcare professionals. Additionally, the National Centre for e-Health runs the patient portal Heilsuvera. The secure website enables patients to renew prescriptions, book appointments and read public health information published by Landspítali University Hospital.

Public transparency

The country shows a strong commitment to timely reporting and sharing information to a wide audience. The Centre for Health Security and Communicable Disease Control reports statistics on communicable diseases through visualizations and reports. Interactive dashboards on infectious diseases and one dedicated to Gonorrhoea, Chlamydia and Syphilis are available online to anyone who wants to inform themselves. Additionally, data related to respiratory viruses (including COVID-19, influenza and RSV) are available during the winter season via another dashboard.

[Explore the dashboards](#)

This was just a glimpse from the report. If you are interested in learning more about key stakeholders and networks, digital infrastructure and legal frameworks which are connected to medical countermeasures, pathogens with high pandemic potential, antimicrobial resistance and CBRN, feel free to dive into the document available at the link below!

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Country visit report – Iceland

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Stockpile Joint Action

Implemented under the EU4Health Programme, JA STOCKPILE - Joint action on comprehensive and sustainable strategic stockpiles of medical countermeasures used in crisis - aims to develop comprehensive and sustainable stockpiles of medical countermeasures (MCMs) ensuring that essential health supplies are available, accessible, and deployable whenever and wherever they are needed most.

The project started in June 2025 and will continue until May 2028. STOCKPILE brings together 54 organisations from 25 European countries to strengthen Europe's preparedness and response to health emergencies.

[More about the Project](#)

From the News: HERA

The Commission's Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (DG HERA) has closed the year 2025 with two important news articles which are both related to investments aimed to help combat antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

Together with the World Health Organization (WHO), HERA has signed a €3.5 million agreement to strengthen the global response to antimicrobial resistance by monitoring the development of antimicrobials and medical countermeasures, developing guidelines for new antibacterial innovations, and implementing the WHO Priority Pathogen Lists to guide research and public health efforts at global, regional, and national levels. In the same period, HERA signed a contract with a consortium of European companies worth €8.85 million which is committed to developing a groundbreaking diagnostic device that will help clinicians select the most appropriate treatment for patients who may require antibiotics. Both investments are helping to fight antimicrobial resistance which already claims thousands of lives across Europe annually and costs healthcare systems an estimated €11 billion.

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